

1 Title

2 Higher soil moisture increases forest temperature buffering

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21

22 Abstract

23 Forests can buffer the understory against temperature extremes often creating cooler microclimates
24 during warm summer days compared to temperatures outside the forest. The buffering of maximum
25 temperatures in the understory results from a combination of canopy shading and air cooling
26 through soil water evaporation and plant transpiration. Therefore, buffering capacity of forests
27 depends on canopy cover and soil moisture content, which are increasingly threatened by more
28 frequent and severe canopy disturbances and soil droughts. The extent to which this buffering will be
29 maintained in future conditions is unclear due to the lack of understanding about the relationship
30 between soil moisture and air temperature buffering in interaction with canopy cover and
31 topographic settings. We explored how soil moisture variability affects temperature offsets between
32 outside and inside the forest on a daily basis, using temperature and soil moisture data from 57 sites
33 in temperate broadleaved forests in Central Europe over four climatically different summer seasons.
34 Daily maximum temperatures in forest understories were on average 2°C cooler than outside
35 temperatures. The buffering of understory temperatures was more effective when soil moisture was
36 higher, and the offsets were more sensitive to soil moisture on sites with drier soils and on sun-
37 exposed slopes with high topographic heat load. Based on these results, it can be expected that, in a
38 warmer climate with longer dry periods, the soil-water limitation of forest buffering will become
39 more prevalent and will likely lead to changes in understory communities. Our results support the
40 inclusion of soil moisture in models and predictions of forest microclimate, understory biodiversity
41 and tree regeneration, aiming to provide a more precise estimate of the effects of climate change.

42

43 Keywords

44 microclimate, evaporation, transpiration, latent heat flux, plant-climate interactions, soil water
45 content

46

47 Introduction

48 Forests can buffer understory microclimate and biodiversity against temperature extremes and
49 drought (De Frenne et al., 2021; Geiger et al., 2012). Compared to open fields with short vegetation,
50 temperatures under forest canopies often show dampened diurnal and even seasonal fluctuations
51 with less extreme hot and cold temperatures during day and night, respectively. This dampening or
52 moderation of temperature extremes is often referred to as the “buffering” function of forests (De
53 Frenne et al., 2021; Lenoir et al., 2017) and as “cooling” function when specifically referring to
54 buffering of warm extreme temperatures. Many forest species, including tree seedlings, are
55 dependent on buffered understory microclimates (Hylander, 2005; Löbel et al., 2018; Scheffers et al.,
56 2014). As the climate is warming, the frequency and severity of heat waves and soil droughts have
57 been increasing and will likely increase in the future (IPCC, 2021). Therefore, the capacity of forests
58 to buffer heat will become increasingly important for forest biodiversity and functioning.
59 Nevertheless, the future buffering function of forests is at risk because it depends on continuous
60 canopy cover and sufficient soil water content (De Frenne et al., 2021).

61 Buffering of daily maximum temperatures in forest understories is the net result of
62 canopy and topographic shading, soil water evaporation and plant transpiration (the latter two
63 together called here *evapotranspiration*), as well as soil thermal inertia, in turn dependent on soil
64 moisture, due to the high heat capacity of water (Ashcroft & Gollan, 2013; Davis et al., 2019; De
65 Frenne et al., 2021). Evapotranspiration is a very efficient surface cooling mechanism as the latent
66 heat flux of water evaporation is high. Forests with a more closed canopy provide a stronger
67 buffering effect because the denser canopies can reflect and absorb more radiation and they can
68 potentially transpire or intercept and evaporate more water (Al-Kaisi et al., 1989; Wei et al., 2018).
69 Dense canopies are also better capable to separate air masses below and above the canopy.

70 The buffering capacity of forests can be quantified by the offset - the difference
71 between the temperature inside and outside the forest (below the canopy and in open areas

72 respectively). The offset has been measured and modelled at different spatial and temporal scales,
73 often with a focus on monthly or seasonal average offsets (Frey et al., 2016; Kašpar et al., 2021; Von
74 Arx et al., 2012; Zellweger et al., 2019). Based on statistical models, temperature offsets have also
75 been extrapolated in space (Frey et al., 2016; Greiser et al., 2018; Haesen et al., 2021; Jucker et al.,
76 2018) and/or in time (De Lombaerde et al., 2022). However, these extrapolations often disregard
77 changes in the local water balance and the effects of overcast skies, moist air and dry soils that would
78 limit evaporative cooling (Davis et al., 2019; Seneviratne et al., 2010). Importantly, the role of soil
79 moisture and its fluctuations has been overlooked in microclimate modelling. Existing models often
80 use spatially variable but temporally static soil moisture estimates (e.g. topographic wetness indices
81 as in Fridley, 2009; Greiser et al., 2018; Macek et al., 2019; Vanwalleghem and Meentemeyer, 2009;
82 Wolf et al., 2021). Continual time-series of in-situ measured soil moisture are therefore needed to
83 explore the potential importance of soil moisture in temperature buffering.

84 The coupling of near-ground temperatures to soil moisture has been demonstrated at
85 local and global scales and the physical principles behind it are well understood (Campbell &
86 Norman, 1997). In the relationship between soil moisture and evaporative fraction, we can expect
87 three contrasting regimes: wet, transitional, dry (Seneviratne et al., 2010). In the dry and wet
88 regimes, changes in soil moisture do not lead to changes in the evaporative fraction (and thus surface
89 temperature), because it is either too dry for plant roots to effectively take up water and support
90 evaporative cooling (dry regime, only found in deserts), or the system is energy-limited and
91 additional water availability would not increase evapotranspiration (wet regime). Only in the
92 transitional regime, we can expect a coupling of soil moisture and surface temperature via changes in
93 the evaporative fraction (Schwingshackl et al., 2017; Seneviratne et al., 2010). Therefore, non-linear
94 responses of surface temperature to soil moisture can be expected when the system shifts between
95 regimes. Though theoretically sound, global-scale analyses like Seneviratne et al., (2010) or
96 Schwingshackl et al., (2017) come with a low spatial resolution (grain size of several kilometres) as
97 e.g. soil moisture estimates are obtained from global gridded climate reanalysis products. Soil

98 moisture varies, however, over very short distances (Ali et al., 2010; Kaiser & McGlynn, 2018; Tague
99 et al., 2010) and up to 80% of spatial soil moisture variation can be lost when aggregating from 30 m
100 to 1 km scales (Vergopolan et al., 2022). Thus, downscaling large-scale soil moisture-surface
101 temperature coupling to biologically-relevant scales remains challenging.

102 At the local scale, understory microclimate cooling has been statistically linked to the
103 local water balance with empirical data for near-ground temperatures and soil moisture (e.g. Davis et
104 al., 2019; Von Arx et al., 2013, 2012). However, soil moisture was either modelled at low spatial
105 resolution and topographic effects were neglected (Davis et al., 2019) or linear relationships were
106 fitted on a subset of days with homogeneous weather conditions, thus missing a large proportion of
107 the temporal dynamics and non-linear dependences (Von Arx et al., 2013). To identify whether and
108 how moisture-driven forest cooling depends on forest structure and topographical context across the
109 landscape, more intensive spatial sampling is needed.

110 Mechanistic models describing the coupling of energy and water exchange among the
111 soil, canopy and the atmosphere could in principle account for the key mechanisms at a fine spatial
112 resolution. Nevertheless, they require detailed information on canopy structure, soil properties and
113 atmospheric conditions to generate accurate landscape-scale predictions (e.g. Maclean and Klinges,
114 2021) and have seldom been validated with empirical data over a wide range of conditions (e.g. Luan
115 and Vico, 2021). As such, they may not provide reliable estimates of the spatial relationships
116 between temperature offset, soil moisture, canopy and topography.

117 In summary, despite attempts to quantify the coupling between soil moisture and
118 near-ground temperature, we know little about the *shape* of this relationship in forest understories
119 as well as about the *interaction* with canopy cover and topographic setting at the landscape scale
120 (Babaeian et al., 2019; Dorigo et al., 2011). The increasing availability and use of consumer-grade
121 microclimate sensors Δ has just recently allowed the continuous monitoring of *in situ* understory
122 temperature and soil moisture with appropriate spatial replication and at a sub-daily resolution (e.g.
123 Wild et al., 2019). With these novel data, we can investigate how soil moisture drives forest

124 microclimate buffering at scales that are relevant for modelling carbon and nutrient balances
125 (Humphrey et al., 2021), for predicting the impact of climate change on species distribution and
126 population dynamics (Woods et al., 2015), and for identifying climate change refugia for threatened
127 species (Greiser et al., 2020; Krawchuk et al., 2020; Wolf et al., 2021). Studying soil-atmosphere
128 feedbacks at the landscape scale is also most appropriate and applicable for climate change
129 mitigation as well as regional and local forest management adaptation to a changing climate
130 (Hylander et al., 2021).

131 In this study, we analysed 57 time series of in-situ temperature and soil-moisture
132 measured during four growing seasons in temperate forest understories in Central Europe. We
133 explored if and how soil moisture fluctuations drive temperature differences between maximum
134 temperatures outside and inside the forest, by linking daily maximum temperature offsets to daily
135 average soil moisture in interaction with canopy openness and topographic heat load, while
136 accounting for daily weather conditions. We ask, whether and when soil moisture drives forest
137 buffering and under which conditions forests can lose their buffering function.

138 Generally, we expect:

139 (H1) Offsets are more negative (i.e., there is more buffering/cooling) with increasing soil moisture, up
140 to a point beyond which a further increase in soil moisture does not lead to a stronger cooling due
141 to an energy limitation (Seneviratne et al., 2010).

142 (H2) The sensitivity of temperature offsets to soil moisture varies with canopy openness and
143 topographic heat load (statistic interaction), because evapotranspiration is affected by incoming solar
144 radiation as well as leaf area, rooting depth and root area which in turn are expected to decrease
145 with canopy openness.

146 (H3) Forests can lose their buffering function when soils get too dry on sites that receive a lot of
147 incoming solar radiation (sunny slopes with more open canopy).

148

149 Materials and Methods

150 Study area

151 The study area lies at the dry edge of forest distribution in Central Europe, in the Bohemian Karst
152 (Fig. 1). The climate is continental temperate with long warm summers, moderately cold winters and
153 a mean annual temperature of 9.8 °C (Neumětely weather station, 2012-2021 period). The total
154 annual precipitation is 546 mm and falls mainly as rain. Dominant forest soils are Cambisols and
155 Leptosols derived from underlying limestones and mudstones (Šamonil et al., 2009). The soils are
156 shallow (<0.5 m) mineral soils with thin humus layer and predominantly silt-loam texture. The soils
157 are mineral, often well drained and calcareous (Hofmeister et al., 2002).

158 The combination of a complex karst terrain with varying soil types creates a mosaic of
159 contrasting forest types with high plant species diversity. Forests cover ca. 35% of the area and are
160 interspersed with grasslands, fields and villages (Fig. 1). Depending on soil conditions and
161 topographic position, the dominant tree species are *Quercus pubescens*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Quercus*
162 *petraea* agg., *Carpinus betulus*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Tilia cordata* and *Acer platanoides*.

163

164 Temperature and moisture measurements

165 For microclimate measurement, we selected 64 forest plots from ongoing vegetation monitoring
166 schemes in the study area (Kopecký & Čížková, 2010; Šipoš et al., 2020). The selected plots extended
167 over ca. 50 km² and cover the vegetation and environmental heterogeneity of the region (Table 1).
168 To reduce potential microclimatic edge effects, all selected plots are situated at least 30 m from the
169 nearest forest edge.

170 At each plot, we measured understory air temperature at 2 m height with a TOMST
171 Thermlogger and soil moisture content of the upper 15 cm of soil with a TOMST TMS logger (Wild et
172 al., 2019). Loggers were protected with standardised white plastic shields blocking direct sunlight and
173 rain (Fig. 1c). TMS loggers were placed inside wire cages protecting them from wild animals (Wild et

174 al., 2019). Loggers were installed during May 2018 and data were downloaded twice a year, before
175 and after the growing season. Only summer data from each year were used (1st June – 31st August).
176 After filtering out potentially problematic measurements and the loggers with incomplete time
177 series, we restricted the analysis to 57 sites (Fig. 1b).

178 As a reference, we used the standard weather station of the Czech
179 Hydrometeorological Institute in the Neumětely village (Lat 49.8542 °N, Lon 14.0375 °E, Elevation
180 322 m a.s.l.). To account for the elevation differences between the weather station and the forest
181 sites (up to 165 m; Table 1), we adjusted daily maximum temperatures measured at weather station
182 with a regional maximum temperature lapse rate calculated through linear regression between daily
183 maximum temperatures and elevation of 35 standard weather stations operating up to 70 km from
184 the Neumětely weather station. As a result, temperatures of each forest plot were compared with
185 slightly different temperatures outside the forest, depending on plot elevation.

186 Daily offsets (in °C) were calculated by subtracting the daily maximum temperature at
187 weather station (elevation-corrected, see above) from the daily maximum temperature inside the
188 forest measured by the logger at 2-m height.

189 Daily soil moisture (volumetric soil water content, VWC, in m^3/m^3) for each site was
190 measured every 15 minutes by a TMS-4 logger using soil moisture sensor based on Time Domain
191 Transmission principle (Wild et al. 2019). To convert raw measurements into VWC, we used a
192 universal calibration equation for mineral soils that was previously tested in the study area (Kopecký
193 et al., 2021). From the resulting time-series of VWC, we calculated average VWC for each day and
194 site.

195 To approximate daily evaporative demand of the atmosphere – which is directly
196 related to the evapotranspiration and hence evaporative cooling – we calculated the daily maximum
197 vapour pressure deficit, VPD_{max} , at the reference weather station from daily maximum temperature
198 and daily minimum relative air humidity using an approximation of the Clausius-Clapeyron equation
199 (Magnus equation) implemented in R package *Plantecophys* (Duursma, 2015).

200

201 Canopy openness and heat load

202 We characterized the sites based on the forest canopy openness and topographic
203 exposure and hence potential incoming solar radiation. The effect of forest density on temperature
204 offsets was approximated by the canopy openness for each site, as estimated from hemispherical
205 photographs. At each site, we captured three upward-facing hemispherical photographs during July
206 2018, using centre-weighted exposure mode and three different exposures (+0.33, -0.66, -1.66 EV)
207 using a Canon 40D camera with a Sigma 4.5mm F2.8 EX DC Circular fish-eye lens levelled at 1m
208 height. Subsequently, from each exposure set, we selected the exposure maximizing the contrast
209 between canopy and sky pixels, converted the selected RGB image to grayscale with 2BG algorithm,
210 classified canopy and sky pixels using intermodes thresholding method (Chianucci & Macek, 2023),
211 and finally calculated canopy openness at the 100° angle of view (Hederová et al., 2023).

212 The potential incoming solar radiation was characterized by topographic heat load for
213 each site derived from a LiDAR digital terrain model with 10 m resolution using the Diurnal
214 Anisotropic Heating function in SAGA GIS (Conrad et al., 2015). This index accounts for slope gradient
215 and orientation effects on received solar energy, but contrary to solar radiation, heat load accounts
216 also for the asymmetrical heating of the slopes, with the highest heat load realized at South-
217 Southwest, 202.5° (Böhner & Antonić, 2009). Heat load is a unitless index, with values ranging from -
218 1 (coolest) to +1 (warmest).

219 While offset, soil moisture and VPD were used as daily fluctuating variables, canopy
220 openness and heat load remained static variables, i.e. the values did not change from day to day or
221 year to year.

222

223 *Table 1. Range of environmental variables covered by the 57 logger sites in the Bohemian Karst. Soil*
 224 *moisture represents mean volumetric soil water content over four summer seasons (1st June – 31st*
 225 *August in years 2018 - 2021). Elevation, canopy openness, topographic heat load and mean soil*
 226 *moisture summaries are based on site-averaged values, whereas daily temperature and offset*
 227 *summaries are based on daily values at each site.*

Variable	Unit	Min	Mean	Max	Source
Elevation	m	287	387	487	Lidar DTM
Canopy openness (summer 2018)	%	3.9	10.4	23.7	Hemispherical photographs
Heat load	-	- 0.48	0.04	0.45	Lidar DTM
Mean soil moisture	m ³ /m ³	0.12	0.22	0.34	TMS-4 logger
Daily maximum air temperature at 2 m in forest understories	°C	12.0	24.3	39.4	Thermologger
Daily temperature offset (forest understory – free-air)	°C	- 8.2	- 2.0	3.8	Thermologger and weather station (elevation-corrected)

228

229 *Fig. 1. Overview of the study area, sampling design and microclimate data. a) Typical forest in the*
 230 *Bohemian Karst and its location in Europe. b) Terrain in the study area with logger locations (black*
 231 *dots) and forests (green patches). c) Sampling design used at each measurement site with one logger*
 232 *measuring understory temperature at weather station height (2 m above ground) and one logger at*
 233 *the forest floor measuring soil moisture in the soil between 0 and -15 cm. d) Summer time series of*
 234 *daily maximum temperature at weather station, daily temperature offsets in the forest understoreys*
 235 *and daily soil moisture (VWC = volumetric water content) for all logger sites in the summer 2018 (1st*
 236 *June – 31st August).*

237

238

239 Statistical models

240 In our analyses, we allowed non-linear responses, which are expected e.g. for soil moisture
241 (Seneviratne et al., 2010) and canopy openness (Zellweger et al., 2019), and accounted for the
242 random effect of site and measurement year by using generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs)
243 and identity-link functions under the assumption of a Gaussian distribution of errors. Before
244 modelling, we reduced possible temporal autocorrelation by using only every 4th day (Davis et al.,
245 2019), which resulted in a dataset with 23, instead of 92, daily values for each summer season. We
246 used this reduced dataset to model temperature offsets as a function of daily soil moisture, canopy
247 openness and heat load (Fig. 2). We included also their three-way interaction to explore under which
248 conditions (in terms of potential energy input modified by canopy openness and topographic heat
249 load) soil moisture drives temperature offsets. To account for the air evaporative demand, we
250 included daily maximum vapour pressure deficit at the reference weather station. As random factors,
251 we used plot ID (to account for repeated measurements from the same loggers) and year (to account
252 for differences in general weather patterns among years, Fig. 3). The model included all predictors as
253 non-linear terms:

254

$$255 \text{offset} = te(\text{soil_moisture}, \text{canopy_openness}, \text{heat_load}) + s(\text{VPD})$$

256

257 where *offset* is the daily maximum temperature offset, *te()* is a tensor product capturing interaction
258 among predictors and *s()* is a smooth term capturing potentially non-linear effect of a predictor
259 (Wood, 2017). We fitted the smooth terms and tensor product with restricted maximum likelihood,
260 REML (Wood, 2011), and used thin plate regression splines with extra shrinkage. This extra shrinkage
261 allows the GAMM to set the smooth term to 0 and therefore to effectively exclude from the final
262 model the predictor with no effect on the response variable (Marra & Wood, 2011). We checked
263 model diagnostics with the function *appraise()* from the package *gratia* (Simpson, 2022). We

264 repeated the analysis for each of the four years separately, using only plot ID as a random effect and
265 the same thinned dataset (23 days per year).

266 We performed all statistical modelling in R version 4.2.0 (R Core Team, 2022) using the
267 *tidyverse* suite of packages for data compiling and cleaning (Wickham et al., 2019), the function
268 *gamm()* from the package *mgcv* to fit GAMM models (Wood, 2017) and the package *gratia* (Simpson,
269 2022) and *ggeffects* (Lüdtke, 2018) for visualizing model outputs.

270

271

272 *Fig. 2. Conceptual figure of the model structure. Daily maximum temperature offsets (Tmax inside*
273 *forest – Tmax outside forest) were modelled as a function of daily soil moisture, canopy openness,*
274 *topographic heat load, their three-way interaction and daily vapour pressure deficit, VPD.*

275

276 Results

277 Temperature buffering in the forest understory

278 Summer season averages as well as the temporal distribution of maximum temperatures (at weather
279 station), vapour pressure deficits (at weather station), temperature offsets (at forest sites) and soil
280 moisture (at forest sites) differed in each year (Fig. 3, Fig. S 2, Fig. S 3). When considering average
281 values, the years ranked in chronological order with 2018 being the hottest and driest year and 2021
282 being the coolest and wettest year (Fig. 3).

283 Forests had on average a cooling effect, with maximum daily temperatures in the
 284 forest understory being on average 2°C colder than maximum temperature outside the forest (Table
 285 1, Fig. 3). The observed temperature offsets considerably varied across sites, days and years (Fig. 3d).
 286 In all years, there were also days when temperatures in forest understories were *higher* than
 287 temperatures outside forests (positive offsets, Fig. 3d). Daily temperature offsets were related to
 288 daily soil moisture in interaction with canopy openness and heat load (effective degrees of freedom =
 289 40.47, $F = 29.91$, $p < .001$; total variance explained by the GAMM: 53%; Table S 1).

290

291

292

293 *Fig. 3. Overview of summer daily values (grey points) of a) VPD and b) Tmax measured at weather*
 294 *station outside forest and c) soil moisture and d) temperature offset measured at 57 forest plots over*
 295 *four years. VPD = vapour pressure deficit, Tmax = daily maximum temperature, WVC = daily soil*
 296 *volumetric water content, Tmax offset = difference between daily maximum temperature inside the*
 297 *forest (measured by a TOMST thermologger) and outside the forest (elevation-corrected weather*
 298 *station data).*

299

300 Higher soil moisture cools the forest understory non-linearly

301 Temperature offsets became on average more negative (i.e., the cooling effect was stronger) when
302 soil moisture was higher (Fig. 4a). As soil moisture at any given site generally fluctuated only over a
303 part of the entire observed gradient (Fig. S 2), the effect of daily soil moisture on daily temperature
304 offsets included also the (intercept) effect of generally wetter sites producing generally cooler
305 temperatures. Temperature offsets responded in a non-linear way to soil moisture, where the
306 sensitivity of temperature offsets to soil moisture was often higher in drier than in wetter soils (Fig.
307 4). In other words, the slopes were steeper at lower soil moistures and shallower at high soil
308 moistures (Fig. 4a), a pattern which was strongest for sites with low heat load values (for average
309 canopy openness, Fig. 4c).

310

311 Canopy and topography effects on forest buffering

312 Canopy openness generally reduced the average cooling effect of a forest site, i.e., temperature
313 offsets were less negative under open canopies compared to more closed canopies (for average heat
314 load, Fig. 4b). Similarly, the average cooling effect decreased (i.e., less negative, sometimes even
315 positive offsets occurred) with higher topographic heat load (Fig. 4c). Together, these results confirm
316 that forest understorey temperatures are generally warmer at sun-exposed slopes and more open
317 forests.

318 We also found significant three-way-interactions, where the relationship between soil
319 moisture and temperature offsets was contingent on canopy openness and topographic heat load
320 (Fig. 4b-c, Fig. 5). Specifically, offset-to-soil-moisture slopes were consistently steeper at sites with
321 higher heat loads compared to topographically shaded sites with lower heat loads (for average
322 canopy openness, Fig. 4c). Low heat load sites, instead, showed a stronger non-linear response to soil
323 moisture with decreasing soil moisture-offset coupling under moister conditions (for average canopy
324 openness, Fig. 4c). For canopy openness, interaction patterns were not as uniform and overall
325 weaker (i.e., slopes were more similar for average heat load).

326 When analysing each year separately, we found differences in the strength of soil
327 moisture- temperature offset coupling with 2019 and 2020 generally showing weaker effects of soil
328 moisture and 2018 and 2021 showing strong effects (Appendix B, Supporting Information).
329

330
331 *Fig. 4. Partial response curves for soil moisture (volumetric soil water content, VWC) averaged over all*
332 *other predictors (a), and in interaction with canopy openness [%] (b) and topographic heat load (c)*
333 *where southwest-facing slopes have highest values. Responses are plotted for average random*
334 *effects and average fixed effects, if not explicitly displayed, e.g. responses in b) are plotted for*
335 *average heat load (fixed), average VPD (fixed) and averaged over plots (random) and years (random).*
336 *The shaded area around the GAMM curve represents the 95% confidence interval. Below the grey*
337 *dashed line, temperature offsets are negative and forests have a cooling effect. Above the line, offsets*
338 *are positive and forests are warmer than free-air temperatures.*

339

340

341 *Fig. 5. Heat map of the three-way interaction between soil moisture, canopy openness and*
 342 *topographic heat load. VWC = daily soil volumetric water content, Tmax offset = difference between*
 343 *daily maximum temperature inside the forest (measured by a TOMST thermologger) and outside the*
 344 *forest (elevation-corrected weather station data). Panels refer to different topographic heat load*
 345 *values, from low (top left) to high values (bottom right).*

346

347 Discussion

348 We quantified the relationships between daily forest understory temperature buffering and soil
 349 moisture along canopy openness gradients in a topographically complex landscape in Central Europe.
 350 We found the buffering capacity of forests to be highly variable in space and time with strong links to

351 local soil moisture, where moister soils cool the understory more effectively than dry soils,
352 confirming our first hypothesis. Further, the soil moisture-temperature offset relationship was non-
353 linear, i.e. the offset sensitivity to soil moisture was higher at the dry end of the observed gradient,
354 indicating rapidly decreasing buffering capacity with drier soils, leading under some conditions to a
355 loss of understory buffering. Despite variations in coupling-strength (i.e. slope) between soil moisture
356 and understory temperature along gradients of canopy openness and topographic heat load and
357 between years, we consistently found an effect of local soil moisture on understory cooling. These
358 findings have important implications for biodiversity conservation, forest management and forest
359 ecosystem structure and function under changing climates.

360

361 Higher soil moisture cools the forest understory

362 Across sites, we found an average cooling effect in forest understories of ca. 2°C, which is
363 comparable to the cooling effects reported from other temperate forests (Haesen et al., 2021; Von
364 Arx et al., 2012; Zellweger et al., 2019). However, we found large variability in offsets from site to
365 site, day to day and year to year (Fig. 3d, Fig. S 3). These spatio-temporal dynamics in forest
366 microclimate buffering were strongly linked to spatio-temporal dynamics in soil moisture (Fig. 4, Fig.
367 5). We confirmed our hypothesis that the soil moisture-mediated cooling effect decreases with
368 increasing soil moisture.

369 The relationship between soil moisture and the offset was non-linear, i.e., the
370 sensitivity of the offset to soil moisture changed along the soil moisture gradient and was generally
371 higher in drier soils, all else being the same. The reduced sensitivity at high soil moisture signals an
372 energy limitation, i.e. more available soil water does not lead to more evaporative cooling (Campbell
373 & Norman, 1997; Pieruschka et al., 2010; Schwingshackl et al., 2017; Seneviratne et al., 2010). This
374 explanation is further supported by the pattern being predominant on topographically shaded sites
375 with lower incoming solar energy, which in turn likely limits evaporative cooling.

376 As we could identify a strong water limitation on understory cooling, especially at the
377 dry end of the soil moisture gradient, we can expect a threshold behaviour of the cooling function,
378 where the cooling effect declines more rapidly when soils dry out even further, up to a point, where
379 forests lose their cooling function completely and understories become *warmer* than open areas (Fig.
380 4, Fig. 5, Fig. S 3). Thus, forest microclimate can suddenly shift from being supportive for
381 buffering-dependent tree seedlings and other understory organisms to being unsupportive or even
382 harmful (Von Arx et al., 2013) – depending on soil moisture fluctuations alone. At the same time,
383 more thermophilic species may become favoured (De Frenne et al., 2015; Govaert et al., 2021;
384 Stevens et al., 2015). Hence, as soil moisture depletion can substantially change forest microclimate
385 regimes, we can expect, on the long run, compositional changes in species communities not only
386 directly in response to changes in temperature, but also as a result to changes in the local water
387 balance caused by reduced water input and/or enhanced evapotranspiration.

388

389 Canopy and topography effects on forest buffering

390 Consistent with earlier findings, the average cooling effect of forest canopies is stronger under more
391 closed canopies (Greiser et al., 2018; Kašpar et al., 2021; Zellweger et al., 2019) and at
392 topographically shaded sites (Dobrowski, 2011; Macek et al., 2019; Meineri & Hylander, 2017). These
393 factors also interacted with soil moisture, confirming our second hypothesis (Fig. 4, Fig. 5). The
394 interaction of soil moisture with canopy openness was, however, relatively weak (Fig. 4b) and
395 inconsistent among the years (Appendix B, Supporting information), probably caused by complex
396 relationships between canopy openness and other vegetation properties that influence temperature
397 via evapotranspiration, e.g. leaf area index, rooting depth, rooting area, as well as complex
398 relationships between atmospheric conditions and canopy conductance.

399 Beside canopy openness, topographic heat load had a strong effect on temperature
400 offsets and was also interacting with soil moisture. Sun-exposed sites with a high topographic heat
401 load were on average less buffered (i.e. warmer), but responded also strongest to soil moisture

402 fluctuations (Fig. 4). Conversely, shaded slopes and terrain depressions were generally cooler, but the
403 offset did not respond so strongly to soil moisture in these topographical settings (Fig. 4). Yet, despite
404 wet and topographically shaded sites being on average slightly less sensitive to fluctuations in soil
405 moisture, these sites provide the largest absolute cooling effect due to less incoming sunlight and
406 more stable and high soil moisture levels.

407

408 **Implications for forest ecosystems in a changing climate**

409 Climate change is threatening forests in various ways. Under rising summer temperatures, forest
410 buffering is increasingly important to avert heat stress for understory biodiversity (Davis et al., 2019).
411 Whether forests can fulfill that function will depend on water availability, which is under threat from
412 increasingly frequent and severe droughts. Temperate forests, in particular, are highly vulnerable to
413 such conditions (Lindner et al., 2010). In north-western United States, projections of forest
414 microclimate buffering based on climate change and changes in water balance show that forests
415 become increasingly water limited and lose their buffering capacity (Davis et al., 2019). These losses
416 will likely be exacerbated by drought-induced crown dieback, pest outbreaks, as well as active
417 drainage and stream regulation following human land use. As a consequence, the buffering capacity
418 of forests as an important ecosystem function is currently threatened and its loss will involve failure
419 in tree regeneration, losses of forest biodiversity and therefore large changes in forest ecosystem
420 structure and functioning. Climate change refugia - locations in the landscape with locally favourable
421 microclimates for threatened cold-adapted species or communities in a surrounding matrix of
422 harmful and deteriorating climate conditions - will therefore be more and more tightly linked to
423 stable and sufficient water supply (McLaughlin et al., 2017). Forest stands with abundant water
424 supply and with moderated energy input (topographically shaded slopes or depressions) may
425 become crucial in harbouring a relatively large proportion of forest biodiversity in a hotter and drier
426 future (Andrew & Warrener, 2017; Hampe & Petit, 2005; McLaughlin et al., 2017). Consequently,
427 forest management plays a crucial role for creating or maintaining supportive understory

428 microclimates, as harvesting regimes and tree species selection do not only directly influence canopy
429 shading levels, but also indirectly impact the water holding capacities of soils, run-off and infiltration,
430 and thereby the cooling effect coming from evaporation. If the aim is to maintain a minimum level of
431 understory buffering, climate adaptation of forest management could include supporting tree
432 species with a high water-use efficiency (Cernusak et al., 2007) and/or high shade-casting ability
433 (Verheyen et al., 2012) on sites that are threatened by increasing risks of soil drought. Since
434 transpiring trees also reduce soil water availability, adaptive thinning could be explored as a measure
435 to mitigate drought-related tree mortality and maintain a minimum level of understory temperature
436 buffering (Sohn et al., 2016). The aforementioned forest management recommendations may apply
437 also to urban environments, where green areas and trees can mitigate the exposure to heat waves
438 (Bakhshoodeh et al., 2022; Wong et al., 2021) with important effects on human health. However,
439 management actions aimed at increasing forest buffering via enhancing close canopies can go
440 directly against nature conservation goals, as the historically open forests host the most diverse and
441 endangered plant communities in central Europe (Kopecký et al., 2013).

442

443 **Model limitations**

444 We focused on analyses at high temporal resolution (daily) while also covering a high spatial
445 replication (57 sites across 50 km²). Interactions among soil moisture, canopy openness and
446 topographic heat load together with daily vapour pressure deficit explained around half of the
447 variation in the temperature offset. The unexplained variation is likely the result of complex
448 mechanisms and interactions between soil, plants and the atmosphere that we could not capture in
449 our simple statistical models (Grossiord et al., 2020; Lenzion & Leuschner, 2009; Massmann et al.,
450 2019; Nalevanková et al., 2020; Oren et al., 1999). Furthermore, we built our models on the
451 assumption that canopy closure is closely related to Leaf Area Index, LAI, and constant over time, but
452 there are likely changes in the overstory and understory vegetation throughout the summer season
453 and between years. For example, Von Arx et al. (2013) found continuous leafing of deciduous trees

454 throughout the growing season and linked that to changes in understory microclimate and its
455 responses to soil moisture. As short-term and long-term changes in understory and overstory LAI
456 affect transpiration rates in forests and thereby the cooling potential of forest canopies, inclusion of
457 these temporal dynamics and the intricate timing of LAI with fluctuating soil moisture and general
458 atmospheric conditions might improve our understanding of (forest) microclimate.

459 When studying daily time scales, one can even expect time lags in plant transpiration,
460 for example when recovering from a dry spell (Gutierrez Lopez et al., 2021), which we did not
461 account for. Further research on soil moisture – atmosphere coupling with the help of simple
462 statistical models should therefore incorporate time lags or look only at periods with homogeneous
463 weather conditions (as e.g. in Von Arx et al., 2013), although the latter approach would result in an
464 incomplete picture of soil water-atmosphere coupling.

465 Eventually, the exact way soil water is coupled to understory buffering can only be
466 resolved with mechanistic models that take into account all elements of the energy and mass balance
467 of a given site (including all drivers of potential and actual evapotranspiration like e.g. soil and
468 canopy conductivity, vegetation structure, rooting depth, wind, photosynthetically active radiation,
469 and delayed plant responses to atmospheric and hydrologic conditions; Luan and Vico, 2021;
470 Maclean and Klinges, 2021; Nalevanková et al., 2020). Semi-mechanistic models, which are detailed
471 enough to capture the main drivers of forest microclimate while remaining simple and
472 computationally efficient, can be parametrized with the currently available data. These models also
473 enable reliable predictions in both space and time. Such models are currently unavailable and simple
474 statistical models like ours can assist in guiding the development of more accessible mechanistic
475 models.

476

477 **Conclusions and outlook**

478 Our study bridges the gap between small and large scales used previously to study soil moisture-
479 temperature coupling in forest understories (Davis et al., 2019; Maclean & Klinges, 2021;

480 Schwingshackl et al., 2017; Seneviratne et al., 2010; Von Arx et al., 2013) by investigating 4-year time
481 series at a daily resolution from a large number of sites within the same landscape (and thus the
482 same macroclimate and forest biome). Our results show the non-linear response of forest
483 temperature buffering to soil moisture and refine knowledge about the topographical context and
484 forest structure, in which soil moisture is a driving factor of forest microclimate. The clear role of soil
485 moisture on forest microclimate calls for improved predictions of future forest understory
486 temperatures, explicitly including variable and changing soil water availability. Our study also
487 questions the recently suggested approach to model microclimate based on the concept of a stable
488 linear slope between macroclimate and microclimate temperatures at any given site (Gril et al.,
489 2022). An important next step towards reliable large-scale projections of forest microclimate under
490 future climate and land use scenarios is therefore to develop models that can be parametrized with
491 the increasingly available time series of soil moisture and near-ground temperature from other
492 biomes and other forest types (Dorigo et al., 2011; Lembrechts et al., 2020).

493 Forests create their own microclimate, which supports understory biodiversity and
494 ecosystem functioning. We demonstrated how vulnerable this temperature buffering function is to
495 soil drought and how forest microclimate refugia may depend on stable soil water levels, which are
496 at risk under hotter and drier future climates. We also found an accelerated weakening of understory
497 buffering when the soils dry out. As a consequence, abrupt and nonlinear responses of forest
498 ecosystems to climate change caused by moisture-temperature feedbacks can be expected in future.

499

500 [Acknowledgements](#)

501 This research was funded by FORMAS [project 2021-01993 to CG], the Czech Science Foundation
502 [projects GACR 20-28119S and GACR 23-06614S] and the Czech Academy of Sciences [project RVO
503 67985939]. We thank everyone helping with the data collection.

504

505 Conflict of interest

506 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

507

508 Data availability statement

509 The Data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Figshare repository at

510 [http://doi.org/\[doi\]](http://doi.org/[doi]), reference number [reference number].

511

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